

DIGITIZATION OF PT.XYZ TEXTILE PRODUCT PROMOTION IN BANDUNG CITY

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Abstract

This research has the objective to explore the impact of digitizing promotional activities at PT.XYZ in enhancing sales volume. PT.XYZ, a well-known textile company in Bandung, employs a descriptive qualitative method for this research. Data were gathered from observations, interviews, and literature studies, including journal references and data tables. The outcomes revealed that PT.XYZ experienced a decline in sales due to inadequate digital promotion. Consequently, PT.XYZ implemented a digital promotion strategy through marketplaces and social media networks, adopting a 4P marketing mix strategy executed via online platforms. The digitization of PT.XYZ's promotions has successfully increased sales, with the company consistently collaborating with influencers to capture audience interest and maximizing digital promotion budgets for effective sales growth.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Promotion, Sales.

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry is a key commodity sector in Indonesia, making a significant contribution to the national economy. It is a labor-intensive industry, with Indonesia standing as one of the global textile producers. Several major players in the textile industry are introducing new innovations, particularly in product development, by incorporating advanced technology. In today's digital era, marketing strategies have evolved to predominantly include digital marketing methods.

These methods are crucial for product marketing, as they expand reach and accelerate sales growth more effectively compared to traditional methods. To attract customer attention, textile companies, including those in Indonesia, continuously improve various aspects such as product quality, human resource capabilities, and consumer service quality.

Over time, the competition in Indonesia's textile industry has intensified due to the emergence of numerous similar companies. The textile industry in West Java, for example, has experienced a downturn. This decline is attributed to reduced export demand and the influx of Chinese textile products into the Indonesian market. PT XYZ, a renowned textile company in Bandung, is known for producing high-quality textile fabrics and fashion cotton that meet both national and international standards.

The company employs continuous process technology in its production, staffed by experienced operators, allowing for substantial production capacity. This enables the company to meet its targets for supplying goods efficiently and effectively.

Table 1: Textile export growth in the city of Bandung in 2019-2021

No.	Year	Total volume (Kg)	Change %
1	2019	18,051,369.70	
2	2020	44,672,134.00	59.00 %
3	2021	37,383,257.80	(16.31) %

Source: BPS data of Bandung city-realisation of exports of main commodities in Bandung city 2019-2021

According to data table 1, textile exports in the city of Bandung saw a significant increase in 2019-2020, rising by 26,620,764.3 or approximately 59% from 2019. This surge positively impacted the company, resulting in an increase in orders and considerable profit. However, in the following year (2020-2021), exports witnessed a substantial decline of 7,288,876.2 or 16.31% from 2020. One of the primary factors contributing to this downturn in orders was the COVID-19 outbreak, which had a profound impact on the Indonesian economy. Additionally, inadequate comprehensive promotion played a role in the decline in orders.

o revive textile products and boost sales, companies often organize promotional programs, hoping to reignite consumer interest and drive purchases. Utilizing various media platforms for these promotions is the most effective method to convey product messages to the target audience (Ardian & Sudrartono, 2021). Promotion mix is a communication tool formed from a combination of advertising tools used by a company (Nurfitri et al., 2023)..

Table 2: The following is the percentage of Bandung city residents who access the internet in 2020

	Male male	Women female	Male + female Male + female (%)
Get information/news Get information/news	72.40	65.83	69.22
Doing schoolwork Do homework	25.27	27.85	26.52
Send/receive e-mail Send/receive e-mail	20.19	16.25	18.28
Social media/social networking Social media/social network	90.63	90.79	90.71
Purchase/sale of goods or services Buy/sell goods/services	20.07	29.42	24.60
Entertainment Entertainment	67.58	61.08	64.43
Financial facilities Financial facility	13.38	11.59	12.51
More Others	2.77	1.33	2.07

Source: People's Welfare Statistics of West Java Province 2020

Table 2 illustrates that internet usage as an information source in the city of Bandung reached 69.22%. Usage for school assignments accounted for 26.52%, while sending emails comprised 18.28%. Social media saw the highest usage at 90.71%, whereas the utilization for purchasing or selling goods was 24.60%. Entertainment accounted for 64.43%, and financial services for 12.51%. From this data, it can be inferred that social media is highly popular among the community in Bandung, while its use for selling goods appears to be relatively low. Hence, there is a need to promote social media platforms to bolster sales, enabling textile companies to maximize their sales and enhance their visibility both domestically and internationally. The presence of social media is expected to rejuvenate sales through digital channels.

Textile Sales of PT XYZ in 2021-2023

Source: PT XYZ Sales Data for 2021-2023

Based on [graph 1](#), it is suspected that the decline in textile sales of PT XYZ in the city of Bandung is due to the lack of maximum promotion carried out, especially digital promotions, while internet users in the city of Bandung are increasing in number every year as listed in table 2. To find out these problems, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title **Digitalisai Promotion of Textile Products of PT XYZ in the City of Bandung** and with research can be found problems experienced by PT XYZ and looking for solutions to improve textile sales increase through Promotion Digitalisation Steps

The era of the Internet of Things (IoT) is centered on delivering value-added services to customers. Some key values inherent in IoT include enhancing production capacity, reducing

production costs, real-time monitoring, and expediting decision-making processes (Maranita, 2022) Hence, the utilization of the internet is highly crucial for companies, particularly in the promotion process. The evolution of digital media and marketing has emerged as a suitable platform for producers to market their products, while consumers can conveniently utilize these platforms as one-stop shops to fulfill their needs (Subramanian, 2020)

According to (Radiansyah, 2022) defines digitalisation as "the use of digital technology to innovate business models and provide new revenue streams and opportunities that generate value in the industrial ecosystem". Meanwhile, digital marketing is a marketing method where all processes and ways of running it have been adapted to the current digital era. (Wahyuni, 2021). The rapid and widespread process of digitization has prompted many companies to develop new digital platforms to address the needs of society. Without digitization, human activities in various fields risk falling behind. Therefore, it is imperative to encourage and expedite the digitization process effectively (Wahyudi & Rahmadi, 2019). (Priyanka et al., 2024) stated Businesses that use digital technology feel better equipped to attract and retain customers through better services and communication channels.

Digital technology is currently developing quite rapidly, this is marked by the industrial revolution 4.0 where industries develop and utilise technology to help simplify their operations. (Nurfalah & Rusydiana, 2019). In the industrial sector, precision and efficiency are paramount in achieving company goals and targets. Hence, the utilization of digital technology holds significant importance, particularly in product promotion. To garner widespread recognition and capture consumer attention, promotional endeavors are executed across various media platforms, including social media and traditional channels.

Promotion is a crucial company activity aimed at introducing products to consumers, thereby enticing them to make purchases (Riki et al., 2023). In promotional activities, it is hoped that it is packaged in such a way that it looks unique and can attract customer attention. According to (Article, 2024) promotional strategies that can be done are:

1. Initiated a focused digital marketing campaign utilizing social media, influencer collaborations, and online advertising to engage with younger demographics effectively.
2. Orchestrated community events and sponsored pertinent social gatherings to enhance brand equity and foster affinity.
3. Developed interactive marketing initiatives, such as augmented reality experiences or gamified applications, offering discounts or special promotions.

According to (Azadi, 2010) The marketing mix is a pivotal internal component of a marketing program aimed at attaining profits through strategic marketing decisions that influence consumer purchasing behavior. According to Kotler, the marketing mix comprises four essential elements: product (product), price (price), place (place), and promotion (promotion) (Lestari et al., 2019)

According to (Scientific & Islamic, 2020) the meaning of 4P is:

1. Product

Everything that is offered to fulfil market needs which include quality, characteristics, brands, packaging, service, warranty and others.

2. Price.

The value of an item measured in money, including price lists, promos, payment terms, credit terms.

3. Place

Related to the distribution process which is an interrelated company activity in order to make a product/service ready for use or consumption.

4. Promotion

Is part of communication that aims to provide an explanation in order to convince potential customers / consumers about the goods / services offered.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses Descriptive Qualitative methods, according to Sugiono in a journal cited by (Adlini et al., 2022) concluded that qualitative research methods are rooted in the philosophy of post-positivism as they focus on exploring natural phenomena rather than conducting experiments. In qualitative research, researchers play a central role as instruments, employing purposive and snowball sampling methods to select participants and sources of data. Data collection techniques often involve triangulation, utilizing a combination of methods. Analysis in qualitative research is typically inductive and qualitative, emphasizing the extraction of meaning from the data rather than generalization. Meanwhile, according to (Hasibuan et al., 2022) Qualitative research is research that uses a naturalistic approach to seek and find understanding or understanding of phenomena in a context-specific setting. The nature of this research is descriptive analysis, namely the regular description of the data that has been obtained, then given an understanding and explanation so that it can be understood properly by the reader. (Syahran, 2020)

In addition, the data sources obtained by the author come from direct observation (observation) and interviews. According to (Waruwu, 2023) qualitative data collection techniques can be done in 3 ways, namely:

1. Observation

The observation technique was employed to directly observe the behaviors and activities of participants at the research location, specifically within the premises of company PT.XYZ. This involved the researcher making direct observations of the various activities taking place in the field.

2. Interview

The interview technique involves extracting information through direct conversation between researchers and participants. In this research, the author utilized interviews to delve into various aspects of the discussed issues and gather comprehensive information.

3. Documentation

Documentation is a technique of collecting information through outcome accurate evidence according to the focus of the research problem.

The author also conducted literature reviews, drawing upon various journal references, and utilized data tables obtained from BPS Bandung City as a reference in this research. This approach was employed to ensure validation aligning with the realities of the textile industry.

DISCUSSION

PT.XYZ, a company entrenched in the textile sector for the past 44 years, initially faced obscurity and limited consumer recognition. Recognizing the pivotal role of digitalization, particularly the internet, in company growth, PT XYZ emphasized its significance. This was crucial for expediting decision-making processes, especially considering a substantial portion of consumers originate from overseas. The company's decline in sales was attributed to underutilization of promotional efforts, particularly in digital realms. Leveraging digital platforms such as television, online news, and other mass-oriented portals with extensive user networks became imperative. Additionally, the incorporation of social media for product promotion facilitated swift, effective, and efficient product introductions. The promotional strategies implemented by PT.XYZ include:

1. PT.XYZ has initiated product launching campaigns with a concentrated effort on introducing new products via prominent social media platforms such as Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram. The aim is to foster vibrant communities through engaging content and facilitate direct interaction with the audience. This endeavor involves collaborating with influencers to leverage their extensive networks for advertising the company's products effectively.
2. A trade show/exhibition organised by the community. The exhibits displayed are in the form of textile industry goods. PT.XYZ itself often sponsors fashion shows to expand its reach to consumers.
3. PT.XYZ has its own application that contains the products produced. In this application contains special offers and discount promos that can be taken by consumers when buying these products.

Based on the author's observations, it has become evident that certain consumers are not aware of PT.XYZ's promotions through social media channels. Consequently, the production process has experienced a continuous decline, primarily due to limited information dissemination about the textile products offered by PT.XYZ, resulting in restricted outreach to potential customers. Furthermore, the utilization of social media for product sales remains relatively low in the city

of Bandung. Therefore, there's a pressing need to digitize product promotion through social media platforms as an effective promotional tool. This approach aims to enhance public awareness of PT.XYZ's offerings swiftly and cost-effectively, ultimately leading to improved recognition and increased sales.

Based on data from internet users in the city of Bandung, it shows that the use of social media is very high with a percentage of 90.71% inversely proportional to the sale of goods / services with a percentage of 24.60%. To balance the use of social media with the sale of goods / services, it is very important for companies to use *marketing mix* strategies in an effort to increase sales, the current strategies carried out by the Company are:

1. Product

The application of the marketing mix, particularly concerning products, is diligently upheld by PT.XYZ in Bandung. The company ensures that all produced items maintain exceptional quality and are crafted from premium materials. For instance, PT.XYZ specializes in manufacturing a diverse range of fabrics, including uniform fabric, shirting fabric, and chinos fabric.

2. Price

Price holds paramount importance for PT.XYZ as it not only captures consumer attention but also significantly influences the company's profitability. PT.XYZ adopts a pricing strategy that aligns with the quality of its products, ensuring that consumers perceive the value of their purchases and feel satisfied.

Additionally, PT.XYZ considers various factors when determining prices, including production costs, raw material expenses, and promotional expenditures. Furthermore, PT.XYZ implements attractive discounts during festival events to entice consumers and stimulate sales. This proactive approach to pricing reflects the company's commitment to meeting consumer needs while maintaining competitiveness in the market.

3. Place

In determining the place in the marketing mix is important because with a strategic place PT.XYZ is easier to reach target consumers. PT.XYZ has official stores that are widely spread in various countries. In addition, there are also online stores one commerce.

4. Promotion

PT.XYZ promotions are carried out to attract consumer attention and increase sales. PT.XYZ itself promotes through social media on PT.XYZ's official Instagram account, website, Facebook. As well as holding new product launch promotions at fashion show festivals.

The company's strategy is very relevant to the results of research conducted by (Sudrartono, 2019) which states that the marketing mix must be continuously used to achieve marketing objectives in the target market.

According to an interview with a staff member of PT.XYZ, the company has intensified its utilization of the marketing mix to reengage consumers and attract new partnerships. Following the impact of Covid-19, the company experienced a decline in orders, resulting in necessary employee reductions to mitigate losses.

Layoffs were primarily targeted at employees with less than one year of tenure. However, with the onset of 2024, the company has begun to experience a resurgence, marked by an influx of orders prompting the opening of new job vacancies. Looking ahead, PT.XYZ aims to leverage the marketing mix effectively in the digitalization era to facilitate rapid growth and expansion.

Digitalisation of product promotion through social media is very important. The more advertisements on social media, the more textile products will be recognised by the public both domestically and abroad. This is relevant to the results of research conducted by (Mentsiev et al., 2020) that digital technology provides tremendous business expansion, which is not possible using conventional marketing and sales methods.

Companies that manufacture their products in one region can effectively promote their offerings through their websites, mobile applications, or by utilizing e-commerce platforms operated by other companies. PT.XYZ endeavors to attract and engage numerous consumers through such digital channels. The dissemination of advertisements across social media platforms has notably bolstered the sale of textile products in Bandung. This approach facilitates broader outreach and makes it easier to connect with potential customers, ultimately enhancing sales opportunities for PT.XYZ.

CONCLUSION

1. The rapid advancement of information technology underscores its importance, particularly in information dissemination efforts aimed at boosting textile sales for PT XYZ. In Bandung, the internet has become a ubiquitous tool, especially for commercial activities conducted on social media platforms. Hence, leveraging digital channels is expected to augment sales in alignment with predefined targets.
2. To bolster sales, PT XYZ executes digital promotional campaigns across various social media platforms including Instagram, Facebook, websites, and other e-commerce applications. This strategy aims to enhance consumer awareness of PT.XYZ products swiftly and streamline the ordering process via online platforms, minimizing waiting times.
3. PT XYZ's promotional strategy encompasses launching campaigns, participating in trade shows/exhibitions, and leveraging its official accounts to promote products. Through these initiatives, PT XYZ ensures that its products remain visible to consumers, bolstered by frequent participation in events and consistent online promotion.

Advice

1. PT XYZ should prioritize the creation of consistent and engaging promotional content by collaborating with influencers and engaging with youth communities that meet specific criteria. This approach aims to capture audience attention effectively and foster trust in the products showcased.
2. It is advisable for PT XYZ to optimize its digital promotion expenditures by establishing an annual budget dedicated to promotional costs. By allocating a clear budget for digital promotion, the company can meticulously track expenses associated with advertisement creation and dissemination. This proactive measure enables PT XYZ to anticipate potential budget fluctuations and ensure efficient fund utilization.

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